

Assessment of the Benefits of Livelihood Strategies Adopted among Youth in Zanzibar, Tanzania

George Julius Babune^{1*}

^{1*}Department of Management Studies, Tanzania Institute of Accountancy, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.

* **Correspondence:** George Julius Babune

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ABSTRACT: This paper examines the benefits of livelihood strategies adopted among youth in the North 'A' District of Zanzibar. A descriptive case study design was applied, while a mixed methods approach was essential to inform the breadth and depth of the topic. The target population were youth sampled by simple random sampling to obtain a 260 sample size. Purposive sampling was employed to interact with the participant. Data were collected using questionnaire surveys and documentary review methods. The quantitative data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics via the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The qualitative data were processed by theme and content analysis. The study revealed that many respondents were engaging in different livelihood activities in the study area. These involved 95 (36.5%) respondents who dealt with fishery activities, 6 (2.3%) respondents who were carpenters, 15 (5.7%) respondents who were tailors, 60 (23.0%) respondents were farmers, and 11 (4.2%) respondents were doing tourism activities. It was found that 6 (2.3%) of respondents were drivers, 40 (15.3%) respondents were students, 15 (5.7%) respondents were businesspeople, 5 (1.9%) were undertaking mechanics, and 7 (2.6%) respondents were teachers. These results reflect the dominance of agricultural and fishery livelihoods in the study

area. It was found that there were expressed benefits related to livelihoods. These benefits involved 70.8% of respondents receiving financial benefits from their livelihood strategies, 85.4% as a source of food, and 66.2% as social benefits, among many others. It was concluded that the youth experience multiple benefits associated with livelihood strategies in the study area. These involve social, financial, skills development, and ownership of properties. Recommended that investment in youth's priority livelihoods is an imperative strategy in attempt to promote sustainable socio-economic benefits at local and national development. Agriculture and fishery skills, being the dominant sectors innovatively have the potential in facilitating youth livelihoods. Hence, they should be adopted and taught in the basic levels of education that accommodates the majority of youth in Zanzibar and Tanzania as a whole.

Keywords: *Benefits, Livelihood strategies, Youth, and Zanzibar.*

1. Introduction

The term livelihood entails a number of activities, approaches, and a framework. It is very extensively used in theory and practice. It usually focuses on individual and community or group capacities that render the shift in youth activities over historical times (Natarajan et al, 2022). According to Der Tambile (2024), livelihood is a famous concept in the body of knowledge and development practice. It is used to mean processes that involve individuals, households, and communities, such as youth, to acquire life necessities like food, water, shelter, clothing, and income. It is argued that individuals, households, and communities' livelihoods over space do depend on the interaction and productive relations with the environment that provide the sources of livelihood, including farming, fishing, fruits, leaves, honey, and herbs. Hajdu et al (2024) conceptualize development as expanding human freedoms, focusing on people's agency, not just in their individual livelihoods but in their capacity to demand human rights and realize change in order to achieve emancipation. The Institute of Development Studies has introduced a dynamic conceptualization of pathways in its 'pathways approach', stressing that pathways that support the perspectives and values of the marginalized could open up routes to social justice. The youth form one of the marginalized groups that require

emancipatory spaces in their rights, freedom, and livelihood promotion. The African Youth Charter defines “youth” as a social, as well as biological, construct – a process of “becoming as well as a category marked by the age boundaries of 15 to 35. In 2007, the World Bank popularized the “transitions” conceptualization of youth, highlighting the five “key transitions” young people must navigate: learning, work, health, family and citizenship (Banks, 2016). Livelihood strategies are defined as those activities undertaken by households to provide a means of living. Livelihood Strategies are diverse at every level. Youth therefore require knowledge, skills, health, family, and citizenship practices (Banks, 2016).

According to the United Nations (2024), there is a historic reversal that threatens the improvements in inequality among countries. The economies of half the world’s most vulnerable countries have been growing at slower rates than those of wealthy countries. This is a challenge to the majority population that comprises the youth majority, who are victims of unemployment and poor livelihoods in developing countries. At the global scale, there are 1.3 billion young people aged between 15 and 24 years old. This is to say, one quarter of the world’s 8 billion population are young people (ILO, 2020). Among this population of youth, 90% live in low and middle-income countries (Chow et al, 2024). Their shift in the labour market has long-term effects on their livelihoods and on socio-economic development in the respective countries (ILO, 2020). The United Nations (2024) highlights that developing countries are not fairly represented in international economic decision-making. This is a hindrance to the required strengthening of their voice and participation as a crucial tool to ensuring a more inclusive and equitable global economic system. Youth involvement in livelihood promotion must be made at the centre of any interventions if sustainable measures are required. One of the interventions is to enhance youth access to education and technical skills to capacitate them to have the freedom and innovative access to resources.

The study on the assessment of future agriculture in the hands of rural youth was carried out. It was found that age, sex, occupation, level of education, and availability of other jobs have a significant relationship with the level of respondents’ perception of agriculture as a profession. Furthermore, the perception of farming

work being tedious, it does not bring daily income, agriculture is for old people, making a choice of career in agriculture is tantamount to choosing to be poor, are the numerous reasons why rural youth do not want to make a choice of career in agriculture in Nigeria (Felicia et al., 2016). Dessie (2024), the lives of young people in the global South have gained increasing recognition in recent years. This is due to the extension of the sociology of youth and youth geographies beyond their traditional disciplinary concentration on the global North (Ansell, 2016; van Blerk et al., 2022). Hasanovic, et al, (2024) indicates that education is regarded as a fundamental driver of social equity and livelihood promotion if well practised. It is argued that the quality of education in the Southeast Europe region varies considerably, reflecting diverse experiences and opinions of the young population. In comparison between 2018 and 2024, data indicates the changes in educational levels of satisfaction in various countries. It was indicated that in 2024, there was the highest level of satisfaction seen in Slovenia, Kosovo, and Croatia. In 2018, the highest satisfaction levels were seen in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, and Slovenia. This is an indication of enhanced livelihoods emanating from access to education that is of high quality. ILO (2024) in Europe and Central Asia, youth unemployment and youth not in employment, education or training (NEET) rates are indicated to fall below. When at 14 per cent in 2023, the youth unemployment rate was 1.4 percentage points below the rate in 2019. There are gender differences in youth livelihood outcomes in the region, which are comparatively smaller than the global averages. In Central and Western Asia, sizable gender gaps indicate the continuing disadvantages of young women. The NEET rate of young women in the subregion was 1.8 times higher than that of young men in 2023 (at 24.1 per cent and 13.4 per cent, respectively). Young population with low levels of education faces severe demerits in livelihood promotion and market outcomes. They have both higher NEET rates than those with higher-level degrees and a higher chance of working a low-paid job. In Indonesia, according to the Australian Government (2023), the youth labour force is large and growing, and is dominated by males. Across different sectors in 2020, 32 per cent of young men (18-30 years old) were employed in agriculture and forestry, and 10 per cent in construction; among young

women. Greater employment opportunities continue to exist in rural areas, and the total unemployment rate is higher in urban areas.

According to USAID (2023), in Africa, there are important opportunities for investing in youth to undergo livelihood transformation in partnerships with governments. The transformation focuses on the multidimensional aspects of livelihood and development, including peacebuilding, youth leadership, and education opportunities. Other aspects include youth economic opportunities, health, food security, and nutritional issues. However, it is important to note that Africa experiences limited access to quality education, secure work, and mental and reproductive health services that hinder the capabilities of youth (Homouchuk et al, 2024). The African Union et al (2024) articulate that social protection in Africa is not adequate in coverage, fragmented, and largely informal. They are fragmented and not adequate in coverage, with only 17.4 per cent of the people covered by formal social protection systems compared to the global average of 46.9 per cent. The existing revamped efforts, in countries like Botswana, exceed the global average with national and rural social protection coverage rates of 57.7 per cent and 68.3 per cent, respectively. In South Africa, youth unemployment (15 to 34 years old) was 37 per cent in 2015, in comparison with an adult rate of 17 per cent (31). But the differences in the age boundaries used to define “youth” make it cumbersome to compare statistics across countries. Betke and Lijfering (2024) globally, international, regional, national, and local level actors in Africa need to develop and implement food systems transition approaches that aim to create positive impacts for the environment and to secure people’s livelihoods, taking into account the capacities of different key actors and societal groups, including youth. The concept of green jobs emerges as a potential solution to enabling African countries to create decent jobs for unemployed youth. This is done by linking the proposed youth employment outcomes to the four types of justice, namely distributive justice, which implies that the formulation of livelihood strategies that support and affect positively the multitude of all actors, including youth. The second justice is the procedural justice, which is based on the extent to which various processes of livelihood are acquired, managed, and coordinated to realise effective outcomes among actors, including youth. The third type of justice is recognition justice. This is to say the extent to

which every group is recognised to receive the same benefits same like all members of the community. The last one is the restoration of justice. This means the ability of the systems to repair and replace losses caused by various factors in the environment, economy, and population, including youth. In Africa, economically, the current growth patterns do not create enough productive and decent jobs for the large number of young people who enter the market each year. In major urban areas where there are relatively better job opportunities, most young people are employed in precarious and low-productivity jobs, most often in the informal sector. The limited alternative decent job opportunities for young people present significant risks to social stability within communities. One such risk is that poor households may have to resort to sending their children out to work (ILO & African Union, 2024). According to Sumberg et al (2024), rural youth show great determination in their struggles to complete their education.

Many youth in sub-Saharan Africa engage in different economic activities that aim to generate income and reduce poverty. So, there is a need for the government to empower the youth by supporting them and strengthening the special fund for youth that can enable them to get financial assistance to run their economic activities in a country like Tanzania to fight against the unemployment problem and poverty reduction. Youth require knowledge, skills, health, family, and citizenship practices. However, they face difficult labour markets, and find themselves in a “transitional limbo”, unable to meet the social roles, expectations, and responsibilities that accompany adulthood across these five spheres. Thus, urban youth across the continent find themselves at a critical juncture, managing current lives and livelihoods while also trying to imagine and move towards their future selves. The contradiction between their increased potential for agency and their inability to act on it leads to anxiety and frustration. The literature conceptualises young people as “waiting”, a term encapsulating their physical, economic, and social immobility and the uncertainty, boredom, and frustrations that accompany it. It is critical to take into account the psycho-social dimensions of long-term unemployment on youth and how it influences their subjective well-being today and into the future. Research on young people’s livelihoods emphasizes their need for ingenuity and resourcefulness as they try to make their way in economies and societies that offer little scope for their

participation, with family networks and community institutions overloaded to breaking point by poverty and unemployment. Many urban youth lack the supportive relationships they need (Banks, 2016).

2. Statement of the Problem

Young people rarely establish an organised presence; however, many are focused on survival rather than longer-term improvements, and network-building tends to represent interdependency rather than individual action and autonomy. With family networks and community institutions overloaded to breaking point by poverty and unemployment, many urban youth lack the supportive relationships they need (Banks, 2016). World Bank Group (2022) argues that in Zanzibar, the large shift of people out of low-productivity agriculture into services, particularly for women, barely contributed to poverty reduction. In Unguja, a large proportion of the poorest parts of the population are in the services sector, suggesting that they have been unable to benefit from the fast-growing tourist industry (Hafidhi (2023). The World Bank Report (2018) shows that about 42% of the world population is young people and children. It is said that there are nearly 1.8 billion youth aged between 15 and 24 years in the world, with the majority of them living in developing countries. The majority of youth are unable to participate fully in society. Around 175 million young people in low-income countries cannot read a full sentence. Among those aged 15-24, some 500 million live on less than a dollar. Hafidhi (2023), findings show that, majority 96 (53%) of respondents agreed that, low level of education is the major factor that hinders youth participation in economic development, 44 (24%) of the respondents strongly agreed that low level of education can hinder youth participation in economic development and only 41 (23%) of respondents disagreed. This implies that for the youth to have a chance for involvement in economic development, they have to acquire a certain level of education in order for them to participate effectively in economic development. Data further show that 90 (50%) of respondents agreed that superiority complex is one of the factors that hinder the youth involvement in economic development, and those who responded strongly disagreed were 44 (23%). The majority, 61 (34%) of the youth sample, showed strongly agree that the inferiority complex is a factor that hinders youth participation

in economic development. These imply that both status (superiority and inferiority complex) have an adverse impact on the youth's participation in economic development.

Hafidhi (2023). The young population in Africa is growing rapidly, and at present, the number of young people aged between 15 and 24 years has reached 50% of the total population. Indeed, the opportunities and constraints of young people's participation in development continue to play a major role. The sector has had continuously high growth rates, which reached 8.7% in 2012. Tourism services are the driver of the observed growth. The trend indicates high potential for employment opportunities for Zanzibar because, by its very nature, tourism services are labour-intensive. MKUZA II target for the service sector is a 7 % annual growth rate, and 12% for the tourism sector, up from the current growth rate of 6.8%. There is a feeling among the local communities that it is people from outside Zanzibar who are benefiting from employment opportunities generated in the tourism industry, leaving the local community to bear the full brunt of the environmental and cultural costs of tourism (Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar, 2018). This called the attention to investigate how youth benefit from livelihoods in the study area. The general objective of this study was to assess the benefits of livelihood strategies among youth in Zanzibar.

2.1 Specific Objectives

- i. To examine livelihood strategies in the study area
- ii. To identify the benefits of livelihood strategies in the study area

3 Theoretical Review

This paper employs the Sustainable Livelihood Approach in understanding and solving the problem. The Sustainable Livelihood Approach (SLA) provides an understanding of the lives of poor and marginalised people by offering a means of poverty reduction (Agarwala et al., 2014). The framework consists of context (shocks, trends, seasonality, and livelihood assets), livelihood strategies, and livelihood outcomes (Scoones, 2009). Livelihood is sustainable if it can access

assets, cope with and recover from stress and shocks, maintain and enhance its capabilities and assets, and provide a sustainable livelihood to future generations (Chambers & Conway, 1992). Natural capital includes land, minerals, forests, wildlife, and fish. Social capital involves social networks, memberships, or association groups to which people belong. Physical capital includes buildings, animal keeping, different machinery, and other furniture. Human capital involves the good health of households, skills, and knowledge of doing different strategies. Finally, financial capital includes savings, bank credit, remittances, or pensions (Ellis & Allison, 2004). Vulnerability, context is pursuing different strategies that are composed of a range of activities that vary from individual to individual or from household to household and is influenced by different factors, such as access to assets, trends (i.e., economic trends) and shocks (diseases, floods and drought) as well as social factors such as policies, institutions and process (Ellis, 2000).

According to Ellis (2004), diversification is a positive strategy for reducing vulnerability, shocks, and poverty, and it is an effective mechanism for reducing the depletion of resources. Youth form one of the vulnerable members of the society in livelihood promotion informed by limited access to capital and resources that this study was framed to uncover how they benefit from the current livelihood strategies.

4. Methodology

The study was conducted in North "A" Zanzibar. This study focused on one shehia, namely the Fukuchani area. This Shehia was selected for the study because of it being one of the rural areas that experienced a high rate of youth who are not employed by the government, and they are employed themselves. But also, it shows that in rural areas, there is a higher rate of poverty compared to urban areas. The study adopted a mixed approach that utilised the potential benefits of qualitative and quantitative approaches in the process of data collection, analysis, discussion, and presentation of results. The mixed approaches were chosen to enable the complementation of results from each approach to respond appropriately to the research questions and variables of interest. A mixed approach was adopted since enabled the researcher to get relevant information concerning the research problem. The qualitative method was used to gather qualitative information, while the

quantitative method was used to quantify the responses and enable the researcher to make objective judgments, as well as provide the rationale to compare and complement the results. The research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted. In this study, the case study design was used because of the need to describe the case broadly with great details using both the qualitative and quantitative methods. The targeted population of this study included the youth of different parts and occupation in the study area.

In this study, both probability and non-probability sampling techniques were used, whereby simple random sampling was used to get an appropriate sample. This technique assumes that all members in the population have an equal chance of being selected to form a sample. The technique was suitable as it avoided bias in the sampling process. Therefore, respondents were selected randomly. Moreover, purposive sampling method was used to select the chairpersons of the villages within the area of the study. A sample size refers to the number of items to be selected from the universe to constitute a sample. In this study, the sample size was 260 respondents. The sample size of 260 respondents was randomly selected because this study provided an opportunity for everyone to answer the desired questions without any kind of bias. Among the respondents 200 were males in the Fukuchani area, and 60 respondents were females. This sample size was obtained using the Yamane's (1967) formula of sample size.

This study applied both types of data collection methods namely primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected through interviews and questionnaire survey. while secondary data were collected through documentary review by reading of journals, and previous reports published. The primary data are the information that are collected for the first time and are known as raw data (Kothari, 2004). These data are collected from the source in a controlled or uncontrolled environment. Primary data are very important in research because data collected through this way whether by observation, interview, or questionnaire surveys are natural data. In this study, a questionnaire survey and an interview were used as methods for primary data collection. This was because primary data collection methods are specific to the motive of the research and highly authenticity

and accuracy. In this study, a structured questionnaire was used with different types of questions, such as closed-ended and open-ended questions, to get relevant and sufficient information about the research problem. It is a better way of collecting data because respondents are required to answer based on their knowledge and experience with the issue, which allows for different opinions from respondents. The interview method for collecting data involved oral verbal stimuli and replies in terms of oral-verbal responses. For key informants, the category of respondents was interviewed using a checklist guide. It was done by both structured and semi-structured questions to obtain information from one person about a particular topic. There was a direct oral interview in which the researcher asked questions to the respondents during discussions. The researcher was cross-examining the respondents about the research problem under study by using pre-determined questions. The responses or information obtained were recorded. Apart from the structured interviews, the researcher also used unstructured interviews. In this study, secondary data are those data or information which has already been collected by someone else and that have already been processed statistically. To obtain the secondary data, documentary review was employed to get the data on the emerging poverty livelihood strategies among youth in Zanzibar. Articles, journals, newspapers, and other previous researches were used to obtain the validity and reliable data. Analysis of data in a general involved several closely related operations which were performed to summarise the data collected by content analysis that involved organizing them in such a manner that it answered the research questions. To analyse the data quantitatively descriptive statistics were used. Devices like computer software packages like Microsoft Office, Excel, and SPSS were used during data analysis. Reliability is a measure of stability or consistency of test scores, or refers to the degree to which the result of measurement, calculation, or specification can depend to be accurate. The study was reliable due to its ability to use the appropriate tools to conduct research. Validity means that a test or instrument is accurately measuring what it's supposed to or refers to how well a scientific test or research actually measures what it sets out to measure or how well it reflects the reality to claims to represent. The study's validity of the information by gathering information from

people with knowledge, understanding, and experience of the problem to be investigated was to be ensured to get accurate information about the problem.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Livelihood Strategies

5.1.1 Respondents' Main Livelihoods

Table 1 presents that, 95 (36.5%) of the respondents were involved in fishery, 6 (2.3%) respondents were carpenters, 15 (5.7%) respondents were involved in tailoring, 60 (23.0%) were farmers, 11 (4.2%) respondents were involved in tourism activities, 6 (2.3%) respondents were involved in driving activities, 40 (15.3%) were students, and 15 (5.7%) respondents were involved in business. Others namely 5 (1.9%) respondents were dealing with mechanics and 7 (2.6%) respondents were teachers. This implies that the majority of participants were dealing with fishery and farming as the major livelihoods in the study area. This also means that many youths in the study area were involved in fishing activities rather than agricultural activities. This is due to the emergence of more economic opportunities such as petty trades, drivers/*bodaboda*, (Motorcycle riders) fishery, food vending. These two major livelihoods done do not require more skill compared to those performed in formal employment, which require writing and/or communication skills and sometimes ICT knowledge. However, critically examining those involved in fishery and farming are not a big number because of the emergency of other livelihoods among youth in the study area. Therefore, fishing is affected in the same way as farming have a smaller number of youth actors. These results concur with another study that found that fishing has been experiencing a decreasing trend throughout the period from 2008/9 to 2014/15 (Adam, 2018).

Table 1: Youth's Main Livelihood Strategies (N=260)

Livelihood Strategies	Responses	
	Frequency	Percentage
Fishing	95	36.5
Carpentry	6	2.3
Tailoring	15	5.7
Agriculture	60	23
Tourism	11	4.2

Driving/riding	6	2.3
Student	40	15.3
Business	15	5.7
Mechanics	5	1.9
Teacher	7	2.6
Sources of Assistance	Frequency	Percentage
Government	37	14.2
Relatives	51	19.6
Others	172	66.2
Type of Assistance	Frequency	Percentage
Money	51	19.6
Education	37	14.2
Others	172	66.2

5.1.2 Reasons for Preference of Livelihoods

The study found that 153 (58.8%) of respondents preferred their work because they did not have another work to do, 67 (25.7%) respondents preferred their activities because it is their hobby, and 40 (15.3%) respondents provided the reason that they preferred their work because they want to be self-reliant and self-determined. This shows that the majority of them, about 153 (58.8%) respondents, supported doing their activities because they don't have any means to get their income except for it. The lack of other alternative employment in rural areas has been termed as one of the reasons for youth engagement in agriculture (Adam & Quinhentos, 2018).

5.1.3 Source of Assistance for Youth Livelihoods

It was found that those 37(14.5%) respondents received assistance from the government in their main activities, 51 (19.6%) respondents said they received assistance from their relatives in their main activities, and 172 (66.2%) respondents received assistance from another source. This shows that the 172 (66.2%) who received assistance from another source, except the government and relatives, were higher compared to the other categories. This indicates that many youth in the study area depend on themselves rather than the assistance of the government and their relatives.

5.1.4 Assistance Received by Youth

The study reveals that about 51 (19.6%) respondents received assistance in terms of money, 37 (14.2%) respondents received assistance in terms of education, and 172 (66.2%) respondents received other kinds of assistance. This means that other kinds of assistance by youth 172 (66.2%) characterize higher influence compared with other categories of assistance received.

5.2 Benefits of Livelihood Strategies

5.2.1 Benefits Related to Youth

Figure 1 presents the benefits of livelihoods among youth in the study area. It was found that, 154 (59.2%) said one of the benefits that obtained from their main activities is being a source of income, 42 (16.1%) respondents said livelihoods activities improve their skills and knowledge, 38 (14.6%) respondents said one of the benefits that they get in their main activities is being a source of food. The last respondents 26 (10%) supported that the benefits got from main activities is promoting self-awareness, self-determination and self-reliance. This shows that 154 (59.2%) the the source of income benefits characterize the biggest benefit among all. This implies that many youths value the income benefits among all benefits that they receive form their main livelihoods. Rural livelihood activities are then defined as a process by which households or individuals construct diverse groups of activities and social capabilities for survival and to improve their standard of living (Ellis, 2000).

Figure 1: Benefits of Livelihood Outcomes in Percentages (N=260)

5.2.2 Financial Benefits

Figure 1 presents the results obtained from the respondents, where by 184 (70.8%) respondents supported as they get a financial benefit in their main activities that they do and 76 (29.2%) respondents were not supporting the existence of any financial benefit in their main activities that they do in their areas. This implies that many youths in that area get financial benefits from their main activities. In rural Tanzania, the youth diversify their sources of income by engaging in other non-farm activities. The existence of financial benefits is an indicator of productive livelihood strategies according to the sustainable livelihood framework among youth in the study area. However, since the majority of youth have small scale strategies the sustainability of these to produce consistent benefits across time is still challenging.

5.2.3 Property Ownership

Figure 1 presents the results obtained from the respondents on property or assets ownership among youth. It was found that 88 (33.8%) respondents supported that they have property ownership, like houses and pieces of land, but in side of 172 (66.2%) respondents did not own any property through their activities. This implies that even though many youth engage in different activities, there is still a problem of low income that prevents them from owning properties out of their livelihoods. These results concur with reasons why rural youth do not want to make a choice of career in agriculture in Nigeria (Felicia et al., 2016). The ownership of properties marks the assets as contended by the Sustainable livelihood framework. These properties are the results of the livelihood strategies adopted. However, due to the sustainability of these adopted strategies mark the required consideration for improvement.

5.2.4. Social Benefits

Figure 1 presents the results obtained from the respondents on the whether or not there are social benefits by youth engagement in the named livelihoods in the study area. It was revealed that 180 (79.2%) respondents supported it as they get social benefits in their main activities, such as good relationships and social interaction, and 80 (30.8%) respondents did not support the existence of any social benefits in their main activities, which they do in their areas. This implies that many youths in that

area get social benefits from their main activities. This related to This relates to results by key informant who explained the aspect of enhancing social interaction among youth in undertaking their activities in the study area. Also Hajdu et al (2024) who conceptualize development as expanding human freedoms, focusing on people's agency, not just in their individual livelihood aspects. Much as youth have individual and collective freedom in undertaking their livelihoods, this is an important part of their development strategies. The results concur with the Sustainable livelihood framework for its core values of promoting strategies that are capable of promoting various benefits. In this case the various strategies adopted by youth produce social benefits among others.

5.3 Conclusion and Recommendations

The research was based on the assessment of livelihood strategies among youth in Zanzibar in the North A District. The study has evidence that the majority of youth respondents were employed themselves through various livelihoods where there are benefits related to livelihood, like the issues of financial and social benefits. Generally, the study found that there are different activities or livelihoods practiced by youth in the area where they live, such as fishing activities, tourism, tailoring, farming, driving, business, and other activities. It was evidence that many youth are benefiting through livelihoods activities like to get income that support their life, to get food that support their life, to improve skills and knowledge through livelihoods activities as well as to be self-reliance. The study reveals that many respondents engaged in different livelihoods activities in the study area where by 95 (36.5%) in fishery, 6 (2.3%) respondents were carpenters, 15 (5.7%) respondents were tailoring, 60 (23.0%) were farming, 11 (4.2%) respondents were doing tourism activities, 6 (2.3%) respondents were drivers, 40 (15.3%) respondents were students, 15 (5.7%) respondents were businessman, 5 (1.9%) were involved mechanics and 7 (2.6%) respondents were teachers. The study concludes that there are benefits related to livelihoods where 184 (70.8%) respondents had received financial benefits from their main activities and 76 (29.2%) were not receiving financial benefits.

5.3.2 Recommendations

Based on the major findings of this study, the following recommendations are found to be relevant to improve youth participation in livelihood activities and their contribution to benefits among youth in Zanzibar. The study recommends that it is relevant to improve youth participation in income-generating in Zanzibar. The findings have evidence that education level has a greater impact on the choice of livelihood strategies among youth. Thus, this calls for special attention from the Ministry of Youth, in collaboration with the Ministry of Education, to work on the improvement of youth's knowledge and skills in various dimensions using both informal and formal education. Specifically, this can be achieved by enhancing training opportunities, capacity building, and skills in different aspects, increasing knowledge, and technology-intensive programs that accelerate economic transformation and rural job creation. The basic level of education should characterize training in fishery, farming, technical and vocational skills and other areas of youth investment preferred. There is a need for targeting policy interventions to ensure youth's access to productive resources such as land for farming, tourism and boats for fishing. The government should upgrade infrastructure, especially roads and other telecommunication services, which will help rural youth connect easily to urban employment opportunities and markets. The government and concerned bodies should enhance programs aimed at poverty reduction for youth in Zanzibar.

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